

IMPROVING SPEAKING SKILLS THROUGH CONTENT LANGUAGE AND INTEGRATED LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

The article gives information about the meaning and usage of CLIL, how CLIL helps to develop the class, aim of the subject, benefits of Content language integrated learning, ways of improving speaking skills by the help of content language and integrated learning.

Key words: *CLIL, knowledge, benefits, advantages, subjects, STT, TTT,*

The basis of CLIL is that content subjects are taught and learnt in a language which is not the mother tongue of the learners.

- ✓ Knowledge of the language becomes the means of learning content
- ✓ Language is integrated into the broad curriculum
- ✓ Learning is developed through increased motivation and the study of natural language seen in context. When learners are interested in a topic they are stimulated to learn language to communicate
- ✓ CLIL is focused on language acquisition rather than enforced learning
- ✓ Language is seen in real-life situations in which students can acquire the language. This is natural language development which builds on other forms of learning
- ✓ CLIL is long-term studying. Students become academically proficient in English after 5-7 years in a good bilingual program

✓ Fluency is more crucial than accuracy and errors are a natural part of language learning. Learners develop fluency in English by using English to communicate for a variety of purposes

✓ Reading is the important skill.

The pro of CLIL

CLIL aids to:

- ✓ Introduce the wider cultural context
- ✓ Prepare for internationalisation
- ✓ Access International Certification and enhance the school profile
- ✓ Develop overall and specific language competence
- ✓ Prepare for future studies and / or working life
- ✓ Improve multilingual interests and attitudes
- ✓ Diversify methods & forms of classroom teaching and learning
- ✓ Increase learner motivation.

CLIL in the classroom

CLIL assumes that subject teachers are able to exploit opportunities for language learning. The best and most common opportunities arise through reading texts. CLIL draws on the lexical approach, encouraging learners to notice language while reading.[1]

Content Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) is a dual-focused educational approach in which an additional language is used for the learning and teaching of both content and language. That is, in the teaching and learning process, there is a focus not only on content and but also on language. CLIL is not a new form of studying language and it is not a new form of subject education. CLIL is an educational approach in which various language supportive methodologies are used which lead to a dual-focused form of instruction where attention is given both to the language and the content: achieving this twofold aim calls for the development of a special approach to teaching in that the non-language subject is not taught in a foreign language but with and through a foreign

language. It opens up doors on an educational experience which can be very hard to achieve in a language-learning classroom. But CLIL is an approach which is neither language learning nor subject, but an amalgam of both and is linked to the processes of convergence. Content and language integrated learning (CLIL) is a method for acquiring content through an additional language (foreign or second) or language with some specific content, hence teaching the subject through the language. David Marsh identified the term in 1994. At first, the idea was connected with teaching business content to business people, and the principal aspect is linked to effective language immersion. CLIL is very important in the world as it integrates the teaching of content from the significant with the teaching of a non-native language. Some scientists prefer to choose an identical theme within the language course — soft CLIL, others would prefer to focus on teaching half of the curriculum in the target language — hard CLIL. There are four components of CLIL:

1. CONTENT

The subjects according to curriculum taught in CLIL consist of art, citizenship, classics, design and technology (DT), economics, environmental studies, geography, history, information and communication technology (ICT), literacy, mathematics, music, physical education (PE), philosophy, politics, religious studies (RE), science, social science and technology.

2. COMMUNICATION

Students should improve communication skills for expressing ideas about subject content and to support students to be active. They need to explain and interpret functions (facts, data, thoughts, and feelings), both in writing as well as orally. Communication skills are vital. Thus, CLIL is aimed at STT (student talking time) and reduce TTT (teacher talking time). To improve meaningful and effective communication the following strategies are utilized:

- brainstorming to introduction and end of topic of study
- open questions
- discussions with each other

- peer feedback
- group feedback
- share ideas with a partner before writing and after writing
- report back on research found on the Internet
- prepare poster or PowerPoint presentations
- role play or debates

3. COGNITION

CLIL promotes cognitive or thinking skills such as reasoning, abstract thinking, hypothesing, creative thinking synthesis, evaluating and so on.

4. CULTURE

‘Culture is at the fundament of CLIL. CLIL gives us opportunities to introduce a wide range of cultural contexts to help students develop positive attitudes and become aware of the responsibilities of global as well as local citizenship. To understand how CLIL works, have a look at [lessons](#) covering various subjects and how English intensifies and provides the learning process. CLIL helps students discover and develop multiple skills — so-called literacy skills. CLIL approach emphasizes on Pluriliteracy skills development through cognitive discourse functions. In other words, you help your students build and structure knowledge according to [higher order thinking](#). Hence your students learn the language to perform and apply it to their field.[2]

The aims of CLIL The aims of CLIL may be different: they range from helping young people understand the point of learning a language to developing advanced language skills; the aims may include getting teachers to change teaching practice (content and language teachers), or increasing levels of harmony between inter-ethnic groups.

Benefits of CLIL implementation: - Language Proficiency. Different approaches in Bilingual education focus on the learners’ proficiency development. Learners acquire the abilities to learn from the second language by ‘developing study skills’. Coonan mentioned that who states that when the learners are engaged cognitively, they learn languages more successfully. Coyle noted that the use of CLIL improves

students' proficiency as they have been exposed to the target language in classes. Accordingly, Dupuy demonstrated that CLIL has not only improved the target language proficiency but also extended both first and second language awareness. Moreover, Mehisto agrees that implementing CLIL synthesizes language abilities rather than focusing on teachers' performance, he also distinguishes that the materials provide some linguistic features and register, which improves students' linguistic awareness. According to Liubiniene CLIL helps to integrate students' language abilities. For this, our teaching experience and our knowledge share the fact that these students are interested in all information related to their specialization. This means that they may develop their skills in CLIL classes and can be observed in their attitude in the class. As a consequence, it proves the value of developing certain skills using CLIL for the reason to improve their study skills, which leads for a better proficiency. Marsh assumes that CLIL programs can develop a feel good attitude among students. This is clear when they achieve higher proficiency level may have a positive effect on their willingness to learn and develop their language competence. Research projects conducted in various contexts have illustrated that the attitudes and motivation to learn a second language can vary not only from language to language but even within the same group of learners and also within different age groups (ibid). A remarkable case is a study carried out in the Basque Country. The study tried to analyze the attitudes towards English of three different groups of students. The first group consisted of students enrolled in the fourth year of primary education; the second one of second year secondary education students and the third one was designed of first-year high school students. The findings showed that the first group held significantly more positive attitudes towards the Second language, whereas the third group presented the least positive ones. The researcher used both psychological and educational factors to explain these results. The third group's reaction would be based on older students' rejection of the school policy as a result of the change from a family identity to a more individual and peer group identity. The other is connected with the various teaching methodologies used in primary and secondary education. In primary education learners

enjoy the oral-based approach and methodologies based on drama and storytelling, whereas in secondary education and high school grammar 10 and vocabulary become obvious and the methodology is usually teacher-centered. The conclusion to be drawn is therefore that there is a failure in attitudes towards the second language due to both psychological and educational issues and this leads us to think whether the use of CLIL approach may help to avoid or at least reduce the effect of the mentioned factors. Implementing CLIL will be an enormous addition for learners and their willingness to learn a second language. Learners often claim that part of their success is related to ability of the teachers. They falsely believe that if they have a native teacher they will gain more but they forgot the fact that teaching is a skill and it is not about only fluency [3]

There are a lot of different people in the world and everybody has different way of studying, the same happens with CLIL process. The American professor Howard Gardner says that there are eight different kinds of intelligence. All of people can be divided into eight intelligent groups: • Linguistic. • Logical-mathematical • Bodily-physical. • Visual-spatial. • Musical. • Naturalistic. • Interpersonal. If a teacher is using the theory about different intelligence, it helps students to produce the information and language in a lot of different ways. If we talk about CLIL techniques using during the lesson, student will have some benefits, such as: - Students learn the same way as native speakers do. - Lessons are based around highly motivational topics using a top down approach. - The content is familiar to students and multiple intelligence friendly. - Students focus on fluency and communication and have the opportunity to experiment with language. The necessity to educate multilingual and multicultural citizens has created the dire need to explore new teaching methodologies that can ensure the learners' command of foreign languages. Content Language Integrated Learning is an innovative method of teaching whereby language is used as a tool for learning both the content of a subject of the school curriculum and the language itself. Although CLIL is not a new trend in Europe, in Greece only in the past few years have some attempts been made to implement it in schools on an experimental basis. The present study

examines the potential of CLIL in the development of the speaking skills of students in the sixth grade of Primary School. Given the complexity of the speaking skill, it is difficult to find ways to explore and assess the learners' oral production on the basis of valid and reliable criteria. Hence, both quantitative and qualitative methods of research are employed in order to provide data for the analysis and interpretation of the results. The assessment criteria of the speaking tests of the national certificate of competence in foreign languages were applied. Observation, of the CLIL lessons, and a questionnaire investigating the students' attitude to the approach, were also applied. The findings, of this research, show the effectiveness of CLIL in the speaking skills of students. [4]

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